

IMPACT OF TOURISM ON GOAN ECONOMY: AN OVERVIEW

Dr. Anthony Rodrigues

Associate Professor & Head,
Department Of Commerce,

Fr. Agnel College Of Arts & Commerce, Pilar-Goa-403203

Goa is the smallest state of India with the largest heart. It is a multifaceted jewel in the crown of Goa. It is a frame of mind and body, spirit and soul. Goa is an unfading memory it is a joy and nirvana. A tourist came to Goa to find some thing different a balm on the busy mind, to enjoy days of freedom on Goa's magnificent beaches, to para sail or swim with the tide of fellow visitors from all around the globe, to savor its unique cuisine and imbibe its spirits, to take a long and invigorating trek in its unexplored inferiors, to marvel at its majestic temples and churches in short, to be at one with the most friendly people in the country.

But then, Goa is much more than just beaches and sea. It has a soul which goes deep into unique history, rich culture and some of the prettiest natural scenery that India has to offer. Much of the real Goa is in its interiors, both inside its buildings and in the hinterland away from the coastal area.

Tourism has a positive as well as a negative impact on Goa's economy because of tourism employs a large number of local Goan people and this adds to the GDP it is because of tourism that a common man in Goa can fill his stomach and the stomachs of his family but if we go to see than a large number of people who are employed or get employment in the tourism sector are not Goans Tourism also benefits the artisans who can earn a living by showing their talents. Tourism also provides employment opportunity to a large number of youth in Goa who can earn their livelihood. A large number of Goans depend on tourism to earn their living. The people who are employed directly or indirectly are the taxi drivers, bike renters, artisans, employees working for GTDC and the department of tourism of Goa, people selling handicrafts, shack owners, Restaurants, hotels, resorts, spa, etc.

INTRODUCTION :

Variously known as "**Pearl of the Orient**" and a "**Tourist Paradise**", the state of Goa is located on the western coast of India in the coastal belt known as Konkani.

The magnificent scenic beauty and the architectural splendours of its temples, churches and old houses have made Goa a firm favourite with travellers around the world. But then, Goa is much more than just beaches and sea. It has a soul which goes deep into unique history, rich culture and some of the prettiest natural scenery that India has to offer. Much of the real Goa is in its interiors, both inside its buildings and in the hinterland away from the coastal area. Legends from Hindu mythology credit Lord Parshuram, an incarnation of Lord Vishnu with the creation of Goa.

Tourism in Goa

Goa is still one of the most unique places in the world and is known as the pearl of the orient. An old Portuguese colony on the west coast of India, it's long been a refuge of freaks and hippies, a centre for trance parties and raves. But it's still great. Whether you come during high season to dance at the parties, hang out on the beaches or get stoned during the monsoon, **Goa** is still one of the coolest places in the world to visit or live.

Tourism is a flourishing industry today. The diverse tourism types are created from the experiences that tourists want to experience; such are the cases of the **nature tourism, cultural tourism,**

adventure tourism, among others. Each type of tourism is a way to give a denomination to a new market niche for a different experience.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study the profile of Tourism in Goa
2. To ascertain the role of tourism in Goa's economy (positive & negative)
3. To study the Role of Government in promoting tourism in Goa.
4. To study the Impact of tourism on Goa's economy.

METHODOLOGY

The required data was collected from primary and secondary sources. To collect primary data a set of informal question were made. The managers in the department of tourism and the Goa tourism Development Corporation responsible for statistics and information activities were chosen as the respondents. Personal interviews were then carried out to gather all the information. Supplementary information was gathered from various secondary sources at the Department and GTDC including annual reports, citizen's charter, brochures, registers etc. Secondary information was gathered through various books, brochures, magazines, in house magazines, websites etc.

Goa as a tourist destination

Since the arrival of the Hippies in the sixties, Goa has been a major destination on the itinerary of international and domestic tourists. The tourist season in Goa begins in late September and carries on through early March. The weather in these months is usually dry and pleasantly cool. Then the weather gets fairly hot around May and by end of June, Goa receives the full blast of the Indian monsoon with sudden downpours and tropical thunderstorms. However it is also during the monsoon that Goa is probably at its most beautiful, with greenery sprouting all around.

Besides the natural beauty, the fabulous beaches and sunshine, travellers to Goa love the laid-back, peaceful, warm and friendly nature of the Goan people. After all, more than anywhere else on planet earth, this is a place where people really know how to relax. Goa, a tiny emerald land on the west coast of India, with its natural scenic beauty, abundant greenery, attractive beaches and temples & churches with distinctive style of architecture, colourful and lively feasts and festivals and, above all, hospitable people with a rich cultural milieu, has an ideal tourist profile.

Although Goa joined national mainstream only after 14 years of the country's independence, tourist traffic to Go registered such phenomenal growth that from 2.00 lakhs tourists in 1975 the figure has shot up to 25.03 lakhs in 2009 of which domestic tourists comprise 21.27 lakhs and foreigners account for 3.76 lakhs.

ROLE OF TOURISM IN GOA'S ECONOMY

TOURISM POLICY GOA

Tourism is essentially an expression of a natural instinct for learning, experience, education and entertainment. The motivating factors for tourism include social, religious, business interests and quest for knowledge. The economic implications of this phenomenon are wide ranging and capable of influencing the development process. Tourism contributes positively to reconciling environment protection, economic development and fight against poverty by creating wealth through economic movement and foreign exchange earnings, contributions to government revenue, spread of economic and social benefits to underdeveloped areas, income and job creation, raised living standards and preservation and conservation of natural and cultural environment. The increasingly recognized human, social, economy and cultural values of tourism need focused attention.

WORLD SCENARIO AND INDIA'S POSITION

Modern advanced means of communication have resulted in massive movement of people throughout the world, drawing them closer, thereby enhancing understanding and appreciation of diverse

cultured, backgrounds and life styles. Tourism has emerged as the fastest growing industry. It is estimated that world tourist arrivals in 1999 were 664.4 million and the world travel receipts in 2000 were approximately 475 billion US \$ which accounts for 11 % of the world's GDP. India accounted for 0.41% of the tourist arrivals (2.7 million) and around 0.66% of the travel receipts (Rs.3009 million US \$). Tourism sector in India is currently the third largest foreign exchange earner after textiles and software. Our vast country has a rich kaleidoscope of natural attractions like mountains, beaches, wild life, rivers, lakes and manmade attractions like historical monuments, forts, palaces and havelis. Unity in diversity is unique feature of our Indian culture and the same is visible through out the length and breath of this country.

TOURISM IN THE STATE

- ❖ Tourism in Goa has assumed the role of major economic activity having direct and indirect correlation with all other sectors. Goa is a unique cultural mosaic with diversity of tourism resources. Planned tourism development in Goa started after three years of Liberation of the Territory i.e. in 1965 with limited funds. Later on , inflow of Five Year Plan funds to the State started resulting in creation of the present tourist facilities though the pace of progress has not been to the desired level.
- ❖ The Goa Tourism Development Corporation was established in the year 1982. The Corporation deals with the operations in the tourism sector and provides budget accommodation, sight seeing tours and river cruises.
- ❖ From a few hundred tourists per year, in the early years, the tourist arrivals have crossed over twelve and a half lakhs in the year 2000.
- ❖ Through the growth in tourist arrivals is impressive, yet more emphasis on qualitative, high-end tourism is the need of the hour.
- ❖ Tourism has been declared as an industry in the state. Annual foreign exchange receipts from the tourism sector in Goa are currently estimated to the extent of Rs.600 crores.

STATISTICS RELATING TO TOURISM IN GOA

Table no. 3.1
Tourist Arrivals (Year Wise)

Tourist Arrivals (Year Wise)				
<u>Year</u>	<u>Domestic</u>	<u>Foreign</u>	<u>Total</u>	<u>% Change</u>
2000	976804	291709	1268513	1.9
2001	1120242	260071	1380313	8.8
2002	1325296	271645	1596941	15.7
2003	1725140	314357	2039497	27.71
2004	2085729	363230	2448959	20.1
2005	1965343	336803	2302146	-6.0
2006	2098654	380414	2479068	7.7
2007	2208986	388457	2597443	4.6
2008	2020416	351123	2371539	-9.5
2009	2127063	376640	2503703	5.5
2010	2201752	441053	2642805	5.6
2011	2225002	445935	2670937	0.98
2012	2337499	450530	2788029	
2013 (Up to Sept)	1789822 (P)	299047 (P)	2088869 (P)	

Source: tourism directory (Department of tourism)

Table no.3.2

TABLE SHOWING ARRIVALS BY FOREIGN CHARTER FLIGHTS DURING SEASON

Arrivals by charter flights season		
<u>Year</u>	<u>No. of fights</u>	<u>Passengers</u>
2000-01	419	116992
2001-02	279	76410
2002-03	384	94350
2003-04	532	126255
2004-05	690	158993
2005-06	719	180310
2006-07	720	169836
2007-08	710	175951
2008-09	615	145428
2009-10	626	137790
2010-11	900	171367
2011-12	910	169006
2012-13	996	215304

Source: tourism directory(Department of Tourism)

Table no.3.3

NATIONALITY - WISE FOREIGN TOURIST ARRIVALS DURING THE YEAR 2011-2012

Sr. No.	Countries	No. of tourist Arrived		%	
		2011	2012	2011	2012
1.	U.K	117683	119891	26.39	26.61
2.	Russia	133780	140100	30.00	31.09
3.	Germany	30234	31842	6.78	7.06
4.	Finland	24972	23787	5.60	5.27
5.	France	17258	19907	3.87	4.41
6.	Switzerland	13199	12951	2.96	2.87
7.	Sweden	15964	18222	3.58	4.04
8.	U.S.A.	8160	8970	1.83	1.99
9.	Australia	6778	6872	1.52	1.52
10.	South Africa	2944	1732	0.66	0.53
11.	Brazil	1294	1203	0.29	0.26
12.	Italy	3211	3952	0.72	0.87
13.	Canada	3656	4507	0.82	1.00
14.	Japan	1963	826	0.44	0.18
15.	Denmark	2541	1562	0.57	0.34
16.	Austria	2185	2201	0.49	0.48
17.	Holland	1383	1282	0.31	0.28
18.	Portugal	1115	1195	0.25	0.26
19.	Ireland	1204	1242	0.27	0.27
20.	Belgium	580	280	0.13	0.06
21.	Norway	446	182	0.10	0.04

22.	Iran	981	0.22	882	0.19
23.	U.A.E.	624	0.14	1262	0.28
24	New Zealand	357	0.08	256	0.05

Source: tourism directory(Department of Tourism)

IMPACT OF TOURISM

Tourism impacting Goa's environment

Goa's unbridled tourism is having an adverse impact on the state's environment and society and also the economy. And the large-scale growth of tourism is leading to increased pressure 'on both society and the environment'. Preserving the national heritage and reducing environmental degradation have become crucial issues for concern. There is a need to examine the carrying capacity of the state. Goa's economy is 'confronted' by a solid waste management problem and that it desperately needs an efficient public transport system. Enough effort has not been made to ensure proper solid waste management. Again, absence of efficient public transport has increased the growth of motorbikes and cars substantially. This in turn has aggravated environmental pollution. The migration of unskilled labour from neighboring states 'on account of the non-availability of unskilled workers in Goa has increased. Other issues include disputes over land use between small entrepreneurs and large corporates, dependence on other states for agricultural produce consumed in Goa, failure to ensure uninterrupted power and the need for improving the quality and quantity of water supply.

A strong positive co-relation does not seem to exist between tourism growth and employment of locals. private transport in Goa is highly expensive in the absence of adequate public transport and taxi operators were working in monopoly power. Growth of tourism might have also adversely affected the poor and downtrodden, especially during peak season when prices usually go up. A proper assessment needs to be done. the tourism sector is becoming a breeding ground of touts and commission agents, which hikes up hotel tariffs and transport costs. There is also an absence of a proper regulatory mechanism to check the price rise. Wide disparity in prices charged during the peak and off-peak season for various services and between the private and public authority needs to be examined. The economy cannot afford to let the tourist be victimized by the private sector..

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

A study was conducted on a number of 100 tourists who came to Goa and 25 hotels in Goa. The data was collected through structured questionnaire attached in the annexure. The analysis of the collected data is as follows:-

Analysis of the questionnaire of 100 tourists

Table no.4.1

Nationality wise arrivals of tourists in Goa

Types of tourist	No. Of tourist
Indian	28
Russian	28
U.K	34
Others	10
Total	100

Source: questionnaire interview

From the above table, we can see that the number of tourists who come to Goa are the domestic tourists followed by the Russians.

Table no.4.2

Table showing Age of the tourists

Age	No. Of Tourists
20 to 30	31
30 to 40	33
40 to 50	26
50 & above	10
Total	100

Source: questionnaire interview

From the above table, we can see that almost 31 % of the tourists who come to Goa are youth who fall under the age group of 20-30 and 33% are in the age group of 30-40.

Table no.4.3

TABLE SHOWING EDUCATION OF THE TOURISTS

Education	No. Of Tourists
Below 10	11
Higher Secondary	25
Graduate	37
Post graduate & above	27
Total	100

SOURCE: QUESTIONARE INTRVIEW

From the above table and chart we can see that the tourist coming to Goa are highly educated and almost 37% are graduates.

TABLE NO.4.4

TABLE SHOWING THE MODE OF ARRIVAL OF THE TOURISTS

Mode of Arrival	No. Of tourists
Air	67
Train	25
Road	8
Total	100

SOURCE: QUESTIONARE INTERVIEW

From the above table, we can see that almost 67% of the tourists come in flight and 25% come in train

TABLE NO.4.5
TABLE SHOWING NUMBER OF DAYS THE TOURISTS WILL STAY IN GOA

No. Of days	No. Of tourist
Less than 5	22
5-10	39
10-15	13
15 & above	26
Total	100

SOURCE: QUESTIONARE INTERVIEW

From the above table and graph we can see that the number of Days a tourist stays here is between 5 to 10

TABLE NO 4.6
TABLE SHOWING THE EXPENDITURE OF TOURIST

Expenditure	No. Of tourist
Less then 1000	8
1000 to 2000	23
2000 to 3000	25
3000 & above	44
Total	100

SOURCE:QUESTIONARE INTERVIEW

From the above table, we can see that the daily expenditure of the tourists is 3000 and above

TABLE NO. 4.7
TABLE SHOWING IMPRESSION OF THE TOURISTS

Impression	No. Of tourist
Good	48
Very good	36
Excellent	16
Total	100

SOURCES:QUESTIONARE

Almost 48% of the tourists have a good impression about Goa but the percentage for excellent is only 16

ANALYSIS OF THE 25 HOTELS

TABLE NO.4.8

TABLE SHOWING THE TYPE OF ACCOMODIATION AVAILIABLE IN THE HOTEL

Types of Accommodation	No. Of Hotels
Luxury	12
Semi- Luxury	10
Ordinary	5
Total	27

SOURCES:QUESTIONARE INTERVIEW

From the above table and graph we come to know that most of the accommodation available in the hotels are luxury and semi luxury.

TABLE NO. 4.9

NO. OF BEDS

No. Of Beds	No. Of Hotels
Single Bed	11
Double Bed	21
Triple Bed	4
Suit	8
VIP'S	7
VVIP'S	2
Total	53

SOURCES: QUESTIONARE INTERVIEW

From the above table, we can see that the double beds available in the hotels are more compared to the single beds, suits, VIP's and VVIP'S

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Profile of tourism in Goa

Goa is the smallest state of India with the largest heart. It is a multifaceted jewel in the crown of Goa .it is a frame of mind and body, spirit and soul. Goa is an unfading memory it is a joy and nirvana. Tourist came to Goa to find same thing different a balm on the busy mind, to enjoy days of freedom on Goa's magnificent beaches, to parasail or swim with the tide of fellow visitors from all around the globe, to savour its unique cuisine and imbibe its spirits, to take a long and invigorating trek in its unexplored

inferiors, to marvel at its majestic temples and churches in short, to be at one with the most friendly people in the country.

Role of tourism in Goa's economy

Tourism plays a very important role in Goa's economy as the revenue generated by tourism is the highest after mining has been banned in Goa. Tourism has become an important source of income to the Goan peoples.

Problems faced because of tourism in Goa

Drugs

The drug trafficking particularly along the coastal stretch has been a damming factor for tourism. The anti narcotics teams claim to have been cracking down on cases but the activity, it is known, is clandestinely happening all over. The narcotics trade has literally started running into the veins of Goa with drugs percolating to the villages which are unconventional places for the banned substances.

Prostitution

Nearly 15 prostitution rackets have been busted only along the northern costal belt in the recent past. The flash trade has also spread its tentacles outside the coastal areas.

International players have also plunged into the illicit trade running trafficking, prostitution and sleaze rackets on the shores of the state via websites hosted in foreign countries.

Infrastructure

Goa has already seen tourists arriving in their private vehicles, cooking along road sides, bathing and even camping in fields and open spaces. Till date the promises of public toilets, changing rooms, parking facilities for tourists is yet to see the light of day

Only a chosen few tourists spots like Baga and Colva are being given a facelift this year. The multilevel car parking project is not likely to be ready this year. Proper approach roads to popularly visited beaches have also been kept on hold and accommodation facilities like camping sited and tenting facilities are nowhere on the agenda.

Solid waste management

Another tourism season comes along with high expectations—increasing charter flights, tourist arrivals and of course not forgetting an additional an additional to garbage in Goa, a tight squeeze on the state's infrastructure, increasing crime, drugs and prostitution all in the name of tourism

While Goa is being marketed and promoted far and wide as a tourist destination, issues concerning solid waste management have been thrown to the winds. Year after year, successive governments promise a foolproof system in places. Sadly files gather dust and waste heaps at places of touristic importance

Despite spending lakhs on contractors, beaches and tourists spots portray a poor picture of Goa tourism with glass bottles, plastic waste and trash of all sorts dumped. To add to the problem are stray cattle drawn to the dump site. This year again, beach cleaning tenders are still in the processing stages and there seems to be no clarity on where the government intends to finalising the same. The proposal for mechanisation for beach cleaning may also add on to the tourism ministry's woes as opposition to use of machines is already started from various quarters.

ROLE OF THE GOVERNMENT IN PROMOTING TOURISM IN GOA

Through the years we have seen a change in the tourism in Goa and this is all because the government is taking under many activities which are relating to tourism. This changes are necessary for the development of tourism in Goa and since tourism is one of the major sources of income to the Goans. But still Goa has not received the best title. The government is also promoting hinter land tourism in Goa.

Impact of tourism on Goa's economy :Tourism has a positive as well as a negative impact on Goa's economy because of tourism employs a large number of local Goan people and this adds to the GDP it is

because of tourism that a common man in Goa can fill his stomach and the stomachs of his family but if we go to see than a large number of people who are employed or get employment in the tourism sector are not Goans

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RECOMMENDATIONS

From the above study divided into 5 chapters we can conclude that tourism has a socio-economic impact on development of Goa. Tourism contributes to the economy and the Gross State Domestic Product to an important extent.

1. In the above study we saw the profile of tourism in Goa and the study shows that Goa has a very rich heritage and a historical background and Goa being such a small place is being recognised all over the world and many international tourists come to Goa every year for tourism purpose
2. The study focused on the role played by the government for promotion and development of tourism in Goa and the impact of tourism in Goa's economic.
3. This study reveals the role played by Department of Tourism and GTDC which are the two agencies of the government. Statistic reveal that the profile of tourism in Goa is changing fast and we can see an increased in the number of arrival of tourist in Goa. And therefore the government as to make improvements regarding cleanliness in the state and preserving the natural beauty of Goa.
4. The government should preserve the heritage and the rich culture of Goa by conducting various activities such as state level Goan folk dances competitions etc.

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